

Governing GeoAI-Enabled Autonomous Driving in the City: A Socio-Technical Governance Perspective

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Abstract

Autonomous Driving (AD) is one of the most prominent application domains of GeoAI and is increasingly integrated into urban transportation systems. While technical research on AD has expanded dramatically in recent years, the governance challenges associated with its deployment remain underexplored. Drawing on governance assemblages and Society-in-the-Loop, this study develops a socio-technical governance perspective to examine the complex relationships between human and non-human actors in governing GeoAI-enabled autonomous driving experimentation. Using Guangzhou as a case study, the findings reveal that AD governance is a complex relational process co-produced across institutional environments, spatial-technical configurations, power relations, and ethical dimensions, in which human and non-human actors dynamically interact to shape governance outcomes.

Keywords: GeoAI, Autonomous Driving, Socio-Technical Governance, Society-in-the-Loop

1. Introduction

The rapid development of digital technologies is reshaping cities worldwide. One prominent example is the application of GeoAI to Autonomous Driving (AD), which has already been introduced into public transport, shared taxis, food delivery, and freight systems (Acheampong et al., 2024). GeoAI refers to the utilization of advancements in artificial intelligence techniques and new data-sharing and data-production practices to support the creation of more intelligent geographic information, methods, and services for a wide range of geospatial tasks (Janowicz et al., 2020; Ye et al., 2025). In the context of AI, GeoAI enables spatial intelligence through real-time perception, mapping, and decision-making based on the integration of geospatial data, sensor systems, and spatially explicit models. With increasing experimentation and commercialization, fully autonomous driving is often portrayed as the inevitable future of urban mobility (Milakis & Müller, 2021). However, AD is not merely a technological upgrade. It involves the introduction of GeoAI-enabled autonomous systems into complex and uncertain urban systems, raising challenges related to safety, regulation, and institutional change (Acheampong et al., 2024; Batty, 2018). Existing studies have focused predominantly on technological aspects, such as high-definition mapping and sensing, often overlooking the complex governance contexts within which AD is

deployed in cities (Gandia et al., 2019). The influence of GeoAI in practice is realized through intricate negotiations among diverse human actors and their interactions with non-human agents (Birkstedt et al., 2023). This calls for a socio-technical governance perspective to understand these implementation challenges.

Therefore, this study aims to bridge this gap by exploring the complex governance dynamics between human actors and non-human agents in urban contexts. It addresses the central question: how do interactions among human actors, non-human agents, and urban socio-technical environments shape the governance of autonomous driving applications? In this study, non-human agents refer to technological systems such as GeoAI-enabled autonomous driving systems that possess the capacity to shape decision-making processes. This study advances a governance perspective on AD, extending the Society-in-the-Loop framework into empirical urban research, and offering insights from Guangzhou, one of China’s leading cities in autonomous driving experimentation.

2. Theoretical Background

To explore the question, this research draws on studies on governance assemblages and the Society-in-the-Loop (SITL) framework. According to research on governance assemblages, “governance is seen as a relational process guided by assemblages that are (re-)produced by a continuous reconfiguration of relations between human and non-human entities” (Albrecht, 2015, p.384). Technologies are not merely governed but actively participate in shaping governance processes (Oldbury & Isaksson, 2021). This perspective is particularly relevant for GeoAI-enabled autonomous driving systems, which operate as spatially embedded AI systems interacting with urban infrastructures, institutional arrangements, and human actors. SITL extends the Human-in-the-Loop approach, which is largely limited to individual oversight and decision-making, by emphasizing the integration of social values, norms, and policies into human–technology interactions at collective and institutional levels (Rahwan, 2018). In the governance of autonomous driving, human and non-human actors, institutional environments, and the relations among them therefore need to be incorporated into governance dynamics (Docherty et al., 2018). Combining these perspectives, this study develops a socio-technical governance framework to analyze how human actors’ values, interests, and power relations are negotiated and shaped by GeoAI-enabled autonomous driving applications within urban governance processes. The framework includes four dimensions: urban physical and technical environments, institutional contexts, power relations between human and non-human actors, and ethical challenges such as accountability and trust.

Building on studies on governance assemblages and SITL, this study proposes a four-dimensional analytical framework that examines how socio-technical arrangements are configured and embedded within AD governance. *Table 1* shows the four-dimensional analytical framework.

Dimensions	Key Elements	Analytical Focus
Institutional Frameworks	Policy and Regulatory Frameworks; Licensing System	How institutional frameworks steer, coordinate and normalize AD experimentation by structuring and managing infrastructural and technological uncertainties within governance processes

Urban Spatial and Technical Environments	Testing Zones; Algorithmic systems; Digital Infrastructures	How urban spatial and technical environments function as material preconditions for AD experimentation.
Power Relations	Human and Non-human Actors; Resources; Authority;	How power is produced and reconfigured relationally through interactions among human actors, infrastructures, and AD systems within specific institutional contexts, thereby shaping authority and decision-making in experimentation practices.
Ethical Challenges	Trust; Accountability	How ethical concerns, particularly trust and accountability, emerge from socio-technical interactions and are negotiated and institutionalized through governance arrangements.

Table 1. Analytical Framework

3. Case Study and Methodology

This study uses Guangzhou as a case study. Guangzhou’s AD development is rooted in its strong automotive industrial base and a relatively favorable experimental environment. Several leading AD technology companies, such as Pony.ai, WeRide, and Baidu Apollo, have established headquarters or research and innovation centers in Guangzhou. At the same time, Guangzhou municipality actively responds to national and provincial policies, not only offering proactive policy guidance and investments, but also collaborating with tech companies and traditional automakers to jointly promote the development and experimentation of autonomous driving technologies. Given its strong policy support and dynamic industrial environment, Guangzhou provides a fertile setting to examine early experimentation and governance practices of AD. The study employs a qualitative research design to capture the complex socio-technical governance of AD deployment. Relevant policies, regulations, and project documents were collected and analyzed to examine institutional contexts. In-depth fieldwork was conducted between November 12, 2025 and January 12, 2026 to observe the physical and spatial conditions of AD testing areas. In addition, a number of semi-structured interviews were carried out with public authorities, company representatives, and autonomous vehicle users to understand how different actors negotiate the development of AD testing areas and how power relations between human and non-human agents are configured in governance processes.

4. Findings

The findings reveal a complex socio-technical governance process of autonomous driving in Guangzhou. Through the interplay of policy frameworks and licensing systems, urban physical environments, and technological infrastructures, AD systems have been progressively integrated into urban governance processes. The integration reconfigures power relations among human and non-human actors and illustrates a situated form of the Society-in-the-Loop mechanism. At the same time, the experimentation process gives rise to emerging ethical challenges, particularly related to user trust, unequal accessibility, and accountability.

In terms of institutional environments, the AD experimentation in Guangzhou is shaped by a set of policy frameworks and licensing systems that function as key institutional mechanisms. A flexible and adaptive multi-level policy framework has been gradually established to steer the development of AD technology. Notably, multiple government departments in Guangzhou have

actively responded to national and provincial agendas and have jointly promoted the development of AD through coordinated policy guidance and public investment. Additionally, some policies at the municipal and district levels have been issued in the form of trial versions, leaving room for adjustments. At the same time, testing licenses also serve as key access thresholds for AD experimentation in Guangzhou. To ensure the safety of AD experimentation, all tech companies and AD developers must follow a graduated licensing pathway before entering the demonstration operation stage. The entire licensing system typically involves several stages of testing, including internal simulated testing, closed-course testing, open-road testing, and long-term demonstration testing. Notably, AD systems play different but important roles in safety assessment at each testing stage, ranging from scenario simulation and driving operation to data generation and analysis. Thus, licensing decisions can be understood as being jointly shaped by both human actors and AD systems, showing the socio-technical entanglement of AD governance. Through guiding policies and licensing systems, Guangzhou's AD experimentation has been directed and regulated by the government, gaining clarity on where and how to proceed. Meanwhile, the agency of AD systems is progressively being integrated into urban governance processes, actively participating in decision-making processes alongside diverse human actors. In this sense, the governance of AD systems constitutes a hybrid process involving human actors, the AD systems, and policy frameworks playing important roles in urban governance processes.

Beyond the institutional frameworks, multiple urban infrastructures and AD technologies have been assembled to support AD experimentation. According to the AD technology roadmaps (China Academy of Information and Communications Technology, 2025), a three-layer spatial–technical configuration constitutes the core of the AD system, which includes (1) spatial testing zones, (2) algorithmic decision-making systems, and (3) in-vehicle and urban digital infrastructures. In the first layer, Guangzhou has opened certain urban physical spaces for AD experimentation. These areas are characterized by relatively low-complexity traffic environments and well-equipped urban infrastructure for testing. The second layer, decision-making system, is composed of algorithms and technologies embedded in AD software, which is the most important part of the whole AD system. According to the interviews with employees of AD companies, the capability of the decision-making system directly affects the processes of AD experimentation and commercialization, as the complexity and uncertainty of real road environments require AVs to handle unexpected situations independently. In the third layer, the AD system is embedded within both in-vehicle and urban digital infrastructures, including various intelligent sensing equipment, data platforms, 5G and C-V2X (Cellular - Vehicle to Everything) communication networks, and high-definition maps (HD maps), which are predominantly invested in and controlled by the Guangzhou government. The interactions between in-vehicle and urban digital infrastructures form a sensing and communication system that enables AD operations in complex urban environments. In general, these spatial configurations and technical infrastructures provide the material and technical pre-conditions for AD experimentation, ensuring the safety and efficiency of AD operations to the greatest extent possible. Therefore, autonomous driving is not an independent technological system but is distributed across and supported by urban spatial and digital infrastructures, which are shaped by governance activities.

Meanwhile, a new distributed power configuration emerges from the interaction of urban institutional environments and spatial-technical configurations, in which local governments, companies, users, and AD systems become highly interdependent. In the case of AD experimentation in Guangzhou, local governments remain the dominant actor in the governance

of AD experimentation through their control over critical infrastructure resources, regulatory authority, and capacity to coordinate multiple actors. Other influential actors include technology, automotive, and autonomous driving (AD) companies, which derive influence from their control over technical resources and accumulated licensing advantages. However, their influence remains structurally dependent on the institutional framework established by the government. Compared with governments and companies that directly participate in AD experimentation, users do not take part in formal decision-making processes. Nevertheless, their usage experiences and behavioral data constitute a critical data foundation for the development and evaluation of AD systems. Finally, AD systems, which comprise AI systems, data infrastructures, and sensing technologies, are embedded in both testing processes and real-world applications. Within these systems, AI agents continuously process data and perform real-time driving decisions. As a result, decision-making processes are fundamentally reconfigured: rather than being solely human-driven, they are mediated by AI systems that link infrastructures, data, institutional regulation, and human actors into a governance process that precedes and conditions human intervention. In this sense, AD systems can be understood as consequential decision-mediating agents within governance processes. Through rapid data processing and real-time decision-making, they shape the thresholds, timing, and conditions under which actions can be taken. Rather than replacing human actors, AD systems reconfigure whether, when, and under what conditions human actors are able to intervene in AD experimentation governance processes. This gives rise to a form of temporal and conditional power emerging from the interaction between AD systems and human actors within broader technological and regulatory frameworks. Through this interaction, AD systems become capable of conditioning decision-making within the governance loop.

Although Guangzhou provides a supportive environment for AD experimentation, current governance arrangements remain comparatively conservative relative to the pace of practical deployment (Xue et al., 2020). In particular, as small-scale testing transitions toward more complex practical applications, ethical challenges such as trust and accountability, have become central concerns among human actors. These challenges reveal tensions between rapid technological experimentation, conservative institutional frameworks, and the involvement of multiple stakeholders. Issues of trust and accountability in AD systems point to an institutional environment that remains underdeveloped, insufficiently transparent, and ambiguous. While existing regulatory frameworks formally distinguish between human operational responsibility and system-induced fault, significant gaps remain in addressing accountability and trust issues in practice. In particular, current frameworks fail to clearly specify how responsibility should be distributed across human and non-human actors, while AD systems themselves cannot be recognized responsible agents. In addition, restricted testing zones further constrain the development of AD experimentation. Due to the strict regulation of testing zones, access to and the benefits of AD technology are unevenly distributed across urban areas. Taken together, these challenges highlight the need for more adaptive, transparent, and inclusive governance arrangements to better address the ethical and practical complexities of AD deployment.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that GeoAI-enabled autonomous driving cannot be understood as a purely technical process, but rather as a socio-technical assemblage. Drawing on governance assemblage research and Society-in-the-Loop theory, the research reveals that the governance of AD experimentation in Guangzhou is a systematic process co-produced through the

interaction of institutional environments, spatial-technical configurations, human actors, and AI systems. At the same time, new power relations and ethical challenges emerge from these interactions. Rather than treating AD systems as passive objects of governance, the findings suggest that they actively participate in governance processes, reshaping decision-making and reconfiguring power relations. More broadly, the findings suggest that the governance of GeoAI applications requires greater attention to the socio-technical contexts in which AI systems are embedded, as well as their capacity to actively transform urban governance processes.

References

- Acheampong, R. A., Cugurullo, F., Staricco, L., & Vitale Brovarone, E. (2024). Editorial: Autonomous mobility transitions—Socio-spatial dimensions and the role of urban planning and policy. *Cities*, 152, 105184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2024.105184>
- Albrecht, M. (2015). Enlightenment in Norway's Oil-Shadow? Governance Assemblages of a Wood-based District Heating Network in Norway's Inland Region. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 17(3), 381–401. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2014.964851>
- Batty, M. (2018). *Inventing future cities*. MIT press.
- Birkstedt, T., Minkkinen, M., Tandon, A., & Mäntymäki, M. (2023). AI governance: Themes, knowledge gaps and future agendas. *Internet Research*, 33(7), 133–167. <https://doi.org/10.1108/INTR-01-2022-0042>
- China Academy of Information and Communications Technology. (2025). **【Roadmap for Intelligent Connected Vehicle Technology (2025–2030)】**. https://www.caict.ac.cn/xwdt/hyxxw/202510/t20251028_697622.htm
- Docherty, I., Marsden, G., & Anable, J. (2018). The governance of smart mobility. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 115, 114–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2017.09.012>
- Gandia, R. M., Antonialli, F., Cavazza, B. H., Neto, A. M., Lima, D. A. de, Sugano, J. Y., Nicolai, I., & Zambalde, A. L. (2019). Autonomous vehicles: Scientometric and bibliometric review. *Transport Reviews*, 39(1), 9–28.
- Janowicz, K., Gao, S., McKenzie, G., Hu, Y., & Bhaduri, B. (2020). GeoAI: Spatially explicit artificial intelligence techniques for geographic knowledge discovery and beyond. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 34(4), 625–636. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2019.1684500>
- Milakis, D., & Müller, S. (2021). The societal dimension of the automated vehicles transition: Towards a research agenda. *Cities*, 113, 103144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2021.103144>
- Oldbury, K., & Isaksson, K. (2021). Governance arrangements shaping driverless shuttles in public transport: The case of Barkarbystaden, Stockholm. *Cities*, 113, 103146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2021.103146>

- Rahwan, I. (2018). Society-in-the-loop: Programming the algorithmic social contract. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 20(1), 5–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-017-9430-8>
- Xue, Q., Xu, M., & Mullen, C. (2020). Governance of Emerging Autonomous Driving Development in China. *Transportation Research Record*, 2674(6), 281–290. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198120918871>
- Ye, X., Du, J., Li, X., Shaw, S.-L., Fu, Y., Dong, X., Zhang, Z., & Wu, L. (2025). Human-centered GeoAI foundation models: Where GeoAI meets human dynamics. *Urban Informatics*, 4(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44212-025-00067-x>